

Figure 4G P-S6 Film

Figure 4G Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4G

Lane 1: Sib-1, Lane 2: Sib-2, **Lane 3: Sib-3**, Lane 4: NIH-1, Lane-5: NIH-2, Lane-6: 16pM1, Lane-7: Failed Line, **Lane 8: 16pM2**, Lane 9: Failed Line **Lane 10: 16pF**

Bolded Text signify the lanes indicated by the arrows

*Failed lines: These were lines derived from the 16pDel cohort with poor NPC marker expression, on quality analysis they were discarded as they did not express PAX6.

Phospha

Gapdh

3.27.18

#1

#2
✓

Figure 4G: GAPDH for P-S6 film

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Lane 1: Sib-1, Lane 2: Sib-2, **Lane 3: Sib-3**, Lane 4: NIH-1, Lane-5: NIH-2, Lane-6: 16pM1,
Lane-7: Failed Line, **Lane 8: 16pM2**, Lane 9: Failed Line Lane 10: 16pF

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Total S6 3.23.18

#1

#2

Figure 4G Total S6 Film

Figure 4G Arrows indicate lanes utilized in Figure 4G

#3

Lane 1: Sib-1, Lane 2: Sib-2, **Lane 3: Sib-3**, **Lane 4: NIH-1**, Lane-5: NIH-2, **Lane-6: 16pM1**,
Lane-7: Failed Line, **Lane 8: 16pM2**, Lane 9: Failed Line **Lane 10: 16pF**

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Total
GAPDH

3.27.18

#1 ✓

#2 ✓

Figure 4G: GAPDH for Total S6 film

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Lane 1: Sib-1, Lane 2: Sib-2, **Lane 3: Sib-3**, Lane 4: NIH-1, Lane-5: NIH-2, **Lane-6: 16pM1**,
Lane-7: Failed Line, **Lane 8: 16pM2**, Lane 9: Failed Line **Lane 10: 16pF**

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